

A STUDY ON PERCEPTION OF YOGA PRACTICE AMONG WOMEN

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Abstract

This study article examines the essential components of women's physical and mental health, acknowledging the inherent potential as well as responsibilities they hold within their families and communities. Because of their many responsibilities, women frequently neglect their own health, which raises stress levels and increases the likelihood of physical illnesses including joint pain, hip pain, and knee pain while also decreasing their quality of life. Women have both physical and psychological challenges as a result of the aforementioned issues and a lack of knowledge regarding their own physical and mental health. This study highlights the need for more awareness and education among women about yoga practice as a means of maintaining their overall health in view of these challenges. A comprehensive and all-encompassing strategy for promoting physical, mental, and spiritual well-being is revealed by kundalini yoga. It is essential for enhancing internal organ health and promoting the harmonious functioning of the body and mind. The benefits of regular yoga practice include happiness, wealth, wisdom, and the accomplishment of life goals. In this context, this study attempts to investigate how women respondents perceive practicing yoga, using a sample of 150 people who were regular attendees at the World Community Service Center, Temple of Consciousness, Pollachi. The study examined how women respondents perceived practicing yoga before and after taking part in Simplified Kundalini Yoga (SKY) sessions using a pre-test and post-test one group design. The findings showed that the mean perception score of yoga practice among women was 33.2756 prior to the intervention of Sky Yoga practice; after the intervention of Sky Yoga practice, the mean score of yoga practice got to 51.5067. Following their SKY yoga intervention, women's perceptions of practicing yoga were significantly different, according to statistical analysis using paired T-tests. The study also clarified the significant influence of demographic factors, such as education, savings, and socioeconomic level, following SKY yoga practice. In conclusion, our study highlights how SKY yoga practice significantly improves women's perceptions of yoga and develops a more comprehensive understanding of its advantages for both physical and emotional health. The study's in-depth examination of yoga practice, supported by research, confirms that SKY yoga has the ability to improve women's general quality of life, including health, education, socioeconomic standing, savings, and spiritual growth. Therefore, the study strongly advocates SKY yoga practice as a holistic approach to improve women's well-being and enable them to have healthier and happier lifestyles.

Key Words: Yoga Practice, Physical and Mental Health, SKY Yoga Practice, Holistic Life.

Introduction:

In today's fast-paced society, it is crucial for women in particular to prioritize their health as a top priority. Women sometimes have to balance many responsibilities in their families and workplaces, which emphasizes the significance of maintaining both their physical and emotional well-being. The article explores the difficulties women have in maintaining their physical well-being, which can frequently result in mental and physical fatigue owing to their abundance of responsibilities. Women today balance their roles in both their personal and professional life by assuming numerous responsibilities. In addition to managing household responsibilities like cleaning, cooking, and providing for family members, they also actively participate in the workforce. Women must prioritize their physical and emotional health above all else in orders to effectively cope with this complicated situation.

Every woman should think about implementing self-care techniques into her daily routine, especially before bed, regardless of where she resides throughout the world. Women's physical and emotional health may be negatively impacted by the immense quantity of time and effort they invest in accomplishing their daily responsibilities. These responsibilities, which are frequently disregarded, include both typical as well as challenging home tasks, leaving little opportunity for women to concentrate on their own well-being. Women may experience physical discomfort as a result of the physical demands of these activities. Neck pain, shoulder pain, hip pain, knee pain, and ankle pain are common complaints. They may contribute to the anxiety and stress that women already face as these medical issues progress. These illnesses have a heavy burden that frequently remains unreported.

Numerous studies have emphasized the importance of leisure activities like yoga and meditation for women to combat physical and mental health challenges. The interconnectedness of physical and mental well-being is a critical consideration. Health is the key determinant for achieving a sound body and mind, with both aspects deeply intertwined. Physical conditions can influence mental health, and vice versa. Women often contend with specific physical challenges, including menstrual issues, menopause, and infertility. These concerns can result in added stress and anxiety, diverting their energy away from various tasks. Support and understanding from family members become crucial in addressing these psychological well-being issues among women. According to the results, women considered yoga to be a beneficial form of complementary medicine. Participants in the survey also mentioned that they felt empowered and enjoyed themselves after doing yoga. A study reported that the individuals appeared to be in a higher state of well-being and physical and mental balance. These results confirm that regular yoga practice has a favorable impact on people's lifestyles and encourages the adoption of practical strategies to improve physical health and general well-being. M. Coco, Andrea Buscemi, et al. (2020). According to a study, practicing yoga increased the experimental group's flexibility indicators more than the control group. I. Sereda, H. Lavrin, et al. (2020). A study reported that Yoga was perceived to have a positive impact on physical and mental health conditions and was linked to positive health behaviors. T. Cartwright, H. Mason et al. (2020).

Women are required to manage both their families and their work environments, necessitating strength in both body and mind. Meeting these demands poses a considerable challenge, demanding resilience and adaptability. The key to overcoming these challenges lies in finding strategies that promote both physical and mental health. Yoga emerges as a powerful tool for women to combat physical and mental health-related problems. Yoga originates from the term YUJ, signifying connection, attachment, or union. It extends beyond being a mere physical exercise and serves as a comprehensive tool for holistic personal development in various facets of life. Its holistic approach, encompassing physical postures, breathing exercises, and meditation, can help women achieve balance and well-being. By integrating yoga into their daily routines, women can enhance their physical fitness, reduce stress, and improve their mental clarity.

Review Literature:

They found that there was a significant result between the variables and yoga practice and mindfulness, body awareness and satisfaction with body image are influencing mediators between the psychological wellbeing and yoga practice. (Benedek T. Tihanyi, et al., (2015). The study found that there was a significant result in reduction of work related stress and increase in autonomic nerve activity after the 12 weeks practice of yoga. The study reported that after the 12 weeks practice of yoga work related stress decreased and found more activeness in autonomic nerve activity. Shu-Ling Lin, SW, MS, Ching-Ya Huang, MS (2015). This study found that the Yoga group obtained more positive results in feelings of clear-mindedness, composure and the level of energy and confidence have increased. Hence, the study suggests more yoga class should be conducted for university employees to enhance their emotional wellbeing and resilience to stress in the workplace. Net Hartfile MS., Jon Havenhand PhD., et al., (2014). The study found that yoga is acted as an alternative treatment for depression and more evidence based research should be conducted to find out the more results. Farah M Shroff and Mani Asgarpour (2017). The study analyzed the impact of yoga on psychological and physical related problems of school and college students. The study recommended that a concrete collaboration is need between yoga practitioners and researchers to find out more significant reasons for the problems to provide a better service to the people. Arun Pratap Singh, (2017). The study reported that yoga practice reduced fatigue in patients with breast cancer but did not reduce depression or anxiety. Chao-Jung Taso, Huey-Shyan Lin, et al., (2104).

Statement of the Problem:

The study's goal is to examine how women manage a variety of obligations at home and at work as they encounter hazardous circumstances in today's fast-paced culture. They frequently unintentionally neglect their physical and mental well-being as a result of the enormous amount of demands placed on them. As a result, many women experience increased levels of stress and worry while also experiencing physical discomfort, including common symptoms like neck, shoulder, hip, knee, and ankle pain. The intricate interrelationship between physical and mental health makes things even more complicated for women, who furthermore struggle with illnesses like menstruation irregularities, menopause, and infertility that take their focus away from regular household duties. Previous research indicates that it is essential to investigate holistic approaches that deal with both physical and mental health issues, as these difficulties are made worse by a lack of family understanding and support. Therefore, yoga is recommended as a promising alternative, but its potential advantages can be overwhelmed by challenges like low knowledge and cultural barriers that prevent its widespread adoption. This emphasizes the critical requirement for providing women the resources they need to prioritize their health and well-being in their complex lives. Various studies on yoga practices have found significant improvements in curing physical and mental health problems, after intervention of various yoga practices. The study recommends SKY Yoga practices to help women communities to overcome various physical and mental related problems to attain healthy, longevity, emotional intelligent and Peace.

Objectives:

- To study the demographic profile of the respondents.
- To assess the perception level of yoga practice before and after the SKY Yoga intervention.
- To analyze the influence of yoga demographic variable on the perception of yoga practice.
- To suggest suitable measures for achieving the perception of yoga of the respondents.

Methodology:

The study was an Experimental research design. The pre-test and post-test one-group design was adopted to study the level of perception on yoga among the women respondents. A sample of 450 women was randomly selected from the list of women who have shown their interest in SKY Yoga (Simplified Kundalini Yoga) at World community Service Centre, Temple of consciousness, Coimbatore district, Tamilnadu. Out of 1500 women, 450 women respondents were selected using simple random sampling. The researcher used a set of questionnaire as a tool to collect the data from the respondents. The questionnaire consisted of two parts namely, Demographic profile and visual functioning questionnaires. The researcher used a questionnaire as a tool to collect the data to analyze the general perception of yoga from the respondents. Demographic profile and a total no. of 12 questions were included in this scale. The pre-test and post-test was conducted before and after the intervention and the data were analyzed using simple percentage analysis, paired t-test and ANOVA to find out the result.

Intervention Procedure:

The SKY yoga program includes Simplified physical exercise, various types of mediation and introspection practices. The SKY yoga practice was given to the participants on weekly two days. Before offering the questionnaire the main purpose of the study was properly instructed to the concerned participants to clearly understand the meaning and purpose of the study. The pre-test data were collected from 450 women participants before they undergone the sky yoga practices. After completion of 12 weeks program the post-test were collected from the concern participants and data were analyzed to find out the results of the study. Total hours of the practice cover 1 and half hour per week over a period of three months (12weeks). After completing the 12 weeks program, the post-test was collected from the concern participants. The practice procedure of Simplified Kundalini Yoga included the following yoga practices.

Practice Schedule:

S.No	Particulars	Time/Hours
1.	Naddi Suddhi	5 Minutes
2.	Meditation	10 Minutes
3.	Simplified Physical Exercise	45 minutes
4.	Introspection	15 minutes
5.	Discussion	15 minute

During the session SKY Yoga practices were instructed to the women participants. In the beginning, Nadisuddhi pranayama practice was given to participants for 5 minutes to set their mind in a normal condition. After 5 minutes Mediation practice was given to them for 20 minutes for achieving a balanced state of mind. Then, the simplified physical exercise was given for 45 minutes for maintaining the flexibility between the muscles and joints. After 45 minutes the introspection practice was given to train their mind in analyzing reason for the problems and find the solutions for the problems. At the end of session, 15 minutes were given for discussion to clarify their doubts and proper guidance was given to the participants to systematically perform the SKY yoga practices.

Table: 1 Demographic Variable

S.No	Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age	25 and Below	80	17.8
		26 - 30	86	19.1
		31 - 35	60	13.3
		36 - 40	99	22.0
		41 - 45	53	11.8
		46 and Above	72	16.0
2	Marital Status	Single	95	21.1
		Married	355	78.9
3	Family type	Nuclear	280	62.2
		Joint	170	37.8
4	Dependents	0	98	21.8
		1	109	24.2
		2	194	43.1
		3	27	6.0
		4	15	3.3

		5	7	1.6
5	Place of Living	Urban	51	11.3
		Rural	374	83.1
		Sub Urban	25	5.6
6	Education	Elementary School	9	2.0
		High School	75	16.7
		UG Degree	224	49.8
		PG Degree	119	26.4
		M.Phil./Ph.D.	16	3.6
		Others	7	1.6
7	Occupation	Student	70	15.6
		Teacher	50	11.1
		Housewives	267	59.3
		Business	22	4.9
		Private	29	6.4
		Government	12	2.7
8	Income	No Income	334	74.2
		10,000 and below	53	11.8
		10,001 - 20,000	31	6.9
		20,001 - 30,000	7	1.6
		30,001 -40,000	2	.4
		40,001 - 50,000	7	1.6
		50,001 and above	16	3.6
9	Savings	Yes	241	53.6
		No	209	46.4
10	In debt	Yes	110	24.4
		No	340	75.6
11	Socio economic status	Lower	9	2.0
		Lower Middle	110	24.4
		Upper Low	187	41.6
		Upper Middle	142	31.6
		High Income Group	2	.4

Analysis and Interpretation: Demographic Variables

The above table shows the result of demographic variables of 450 women respondents. Out of 450 respondents, 99 (22.0%) of them were between the age group of 36-40. Out of 450 respondents 355(78.9%) of them got married. A total of 280 (62.2%) women respondents who belonged to the Nuclear family. Out of 450 respondents, 194(43.1%) of them have two dependents, 374(83.1%) of them are belonged to rural area, 224(49.8%) of them have completed them under graduation. Out of 450 respondents, 267(59.3%) of them are housewives, 334(74.2%) of them had no income source, out of 450 respondents, 241(53.6%) of them had savings. Out of 450 respondents, 340(75.6%) of them don't have any debt, the above table shows that out of 450 respondents, 187(41.6%) of them are in the Upper low state.

Table 2: Significance Test for Perception on Yoga Based on Demographic Variables

S.No	Variable	Test	Values	Result
1.	Age	Anova	F = 0.335, Significance = 0.892	Not Significant
2.	Marital Status	T-test	F = 3.251, Significance = 0.072	Not Significant
3.	Family type	T-test	F = 0.241, Significance = 0.624	Not Significant
4.	Dependents	Anova	F = 0.389, Significance = 0.857	Not Significant
5.	Place of Living	Anova	F = 1.009, Significance = 0.365	Not Significant
6.	Education	Anova	F = 3.713, Significance = .003	Significant
7.	Occupation	Anova	F = .964, Significance = .439	Not Significant
8.	Income	Anova	F = 1.138, Significance = .339	Not Significant
9.	Savings	T-test	F = 1.135, Significance = .287	Significant
10.	In debt	T-test	F = 3.758, Significance = .053	Not Significant
11.	Socio Economic Status	Anova	F = 2.995, Significance = .019	Significant

There is a significant difference in perception on yoga based on and Education, savings and Socio economic status. There is not a significant difference in perception on yoga based on age, Marital Status, family type, dependents, Place of Living, occupation, income and in debt. Therefore, it is concluded that the variables

of Education, savings and Socio economic status have greatly influenced the perception on yoga with women respondents.

Table 3: Overall Perception on Yoga practice before and after the SKY Yoga intervention

S.No	Particulars	Before		After	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Very Good (40-60)	82	18.2	55	12.2
2.	Good (35-39)	100	22.2	196	43.6
3.	Neutral (27-34)	191	42.4	132	29.3
4.	Poor (16-26)	75	16.7	63	14.0
5.	Very Poor (12-15)	2	.4	4	.9
	Mean Value	33.2756		51.5067	
	t-value = -43.188	Df = 449		Sig. (2-tailed) = .000	

The above table shows the result of overall perception about the yoga practices and its impact. Before undergone the practice the perception level was neutral among 191(42.4%). But after the practice the perception level significantly has changed to good 196 (43.6). Therefore, the study found that there was a significant change has occurred after the practice in positive perception on yoga practice among the respondents. The perception on yoga of respondents before practicing SKY Yoga reveals that the mean value was found at 33.2756, but after practicing SKY Yoga the mean value of the respondents increased which was found to be at 51.5067. Besides, it is understood that there is a significant difference found in the mean values, but it needs to be scientifically proven, then the paired T-test was performed. The paired T-test value is (-43.188) shows that there is a significant difference in the perception on yoga of the respondents before SKY Yoga practices and after SKY Yoga practices.

Thus, from the mean value, it is concluded that after the SKY Yoga practice the perception on yoga of the respondents has increased considerably. Therefore, it is concluded that the SKY Yoga practice improves or has a meaningful outcome on the perception on yoga of respondents.

Discussion:

This study mainly discusses the perception on yoga and how the yoga has supported to provide healthy body and mind. The habit of practicing yoga is increasing as they have more knowledge about the importance of yoga and its benefits. Yoga has become a part of our life and supported a lot to get rid of various types of physical related problems. The factors like food, nature of work, life style change and genetic have totally led to chronic diseases like diabetes, heart and kidney related problem. As a result human life has mostly suffered with these problems and also has led to many psychological related problems. With the support of physical energy all kinds of activities are made to survive and to live a long life in this world. So, the body condition has to be maintained until death to avoid disease free live. Numerous studies have found out that proper physical exercise can help to cure maximum of physical related problems such as hip pain, joint pain, arthodise, diabetes, blood pressure, menstrual problems. The people with support of education have gained more knowledge about the concepts of yoga and how it is significance for life and carries. Yoga practices are the best alternative treatment for physical and mental related problems which is universally accepted one. People are now having the habit of doing yoga regularly and they have as a passion in their life. In addition to, more research related articles are published related to yoga benefits which are accessed by the educated people. On the basis of the research, people sometimes take certain important decision that mostly support the body and mind for being health. Healthy lifestyle, food habits, Yoga and meditation are the key factors to keep the body and mind fit and also it helps to achieve economic growth and satisfaction in life.

In this study, the independent variables like education, savings and socio economic status have highly influenced by the perception of yoga among women respondents. Therefore, the perception of yoga practices has highly impacted in producing the overall health for the body and mind of the women respondents.

Conclusion:

Thus, the study has concluded that yoga practices can help them to solve the physical related problems. Moreover, they are able to balance their mind between work and life. So, this study recommended yoga practices specifically for women to overcome from all kinds of health related problems as they play multi-play role in family and in the office. So they have to practice yoga regularly to strengthen their body and balance their emotional moods in work and life. The government has to establish more health center and counseling cell for all women communities to provide solutions along with yoga practices. Yoga practice should be incorporated into all the village people and the physical education curriculum for public and students so that they can learn about this technique for increasing flexibility.

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